

Correlational Analysis of Staff Motivation and Job Satisfaction of Library Personnel in Public Universities in Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Job satisfaction plays a crucial role in organisational effectiveness, including within public university libraries. This study investigates the factors contributing to declining job satisfaction levels among library personnel in Oyo State, Nigeria, identifying key factors such as limited career prospects opportunities, job insecurity, poor work environment, and non-competitive salaries. The study involved a comprehensive survey of 139 library personnel across four public universities in Oyo State: University of Ibadan, Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Technical University, and Emmanuel Alayande University of Education. Employing a total enumeration approach, the study ensured all library personnel participated, thus enhancing the representativeness of the findings. Data were collected using validated questionnaires, which demonstrated high reliability (Cronbach's alpha ≥ 0.7). Statistical analysis revealed a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.420$) between staff motivation and job satisfaction, suggesting that motivated employees are more likely to report higher satisfaction levels. Based on these findings, the study recommends the implementation of targeted policies aimed at enhancing staff motivation through career development programmes, improved working conditions, and competitive remuneration. By acknowledging and addressing these motivational

factors, public university libraries in Oyo State can improve job satisfaction and overall organisational performance, ultimately benefiting both library personnel and the communities they serve.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Library Personnel, Public Universities, Staff Motivation, Nigeria.

Introduction

A job is a task performed by an individual or group in exchange for compensation. In this context, the researchers define a job as a paid position in regular employment. Job satisfaction refers to an individual's feelings about events, rewards, relationships, and overall mental well-being at work (Yaya, 2016). Job satisfaction is influenced by internal feelings, which can lead to a sense of fulfillment when expectations are met. A worker's job satisfaction has been a major issue in the fields of human resources, psychology, and organisations (Mabaso and Dlamini, 2017). Job satisfaction has been defined by Ezeamama (2019) as the level to which workers like their work. It is the attitude displayed by workers towards their jobs. Job satisfaction involves doing a job one loves, doing it well, and being compensated. It can also be described as the attitude of employees towards their wages, working conditions, promotions, and recognition. It is an essential factor for personal fulfillment in the course of carrying out one's duty (Opeke et al., 2019) Job satisfaction is essential for workers to remain committed and improve their performance in their organisations. Lack of job satisfaction could result in low productivity and inefficiency (Adewoyin et al., 2020).

Factors contributing to job satisfaction among employees including library personnel are: job security,

recognition from colleagues, fair and consistent pay, opportunities for career growth, a supportive work environment, and chances for advancement. While extensive research has been conducted on job satisfaction in librarianship, there is a notable lack of emphasis on understanding what truly satisfies library personnel compared to professionals in other fields. Much of the literature on librarianship has focused on meeting the needs of library patrons and making materials accessible to them, overlooking the importance of library personnel job satisfaction. It is crucial to recognise that librarians, like other professionals, require quality job satisfaction to enhance their efficiency in university libraries. Yaya et al. (2016) suggest that job satisfaction boosts workers' efficiency, particularly in academic libraries, as satisfied workers tend to be happier and more productive.

Motivation encompasses a range of internal factors, such as desires, urges, wishes, and needs that drive and sustain behaviour toward a goal (Edeh, 2010). Edeh further characterises motivation as the logical and initiative processes through which individuals strive to fulfill fundamental desires, personal goals, and perceived requirements that influence human actions. In the context of the library system, staff motivation plays a crucial role in inspiring library staff to work independently or collaboratively to achieve optimal results. It represents the willingness to exert significant effort towards organisational objectives in exchange for fulfilling individual needs. Two key dimensions are commonly used to assess motivation: intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation refers to the internal drive that originates within an individual. Library personnel may be motivated to complete tasks because it provides them with a sense of accomplishment, mastery, and self-fulfillment. Intrinsic motivation is "associated with the enjoyment, interest, and satisfaction derived from the task itself. On the other hand, extrinsic motivation is an external factor that influences staff motivation. It involves seeking external rewards such as financial incentives, perks, promotions, and recognition in return for job satisfaction (Dina and Olowosoke, 2018).

Given this background, the importance of staff motivation and job satisfaction in retaining skilled and dedicated library personnel cannot be overstated. Consequently, there is a need to explore the impact of staff motivation on the job satisfaction of library personnel to enhance overall performance and employee retention in the library setting.

Statement of the Problem

Ensuring job satisfaction in every organisation is very crucial, as it directly impacts employee happiness, engagement, and productivity. All of which are essential for achieving organisational goals. Recent studies indicate a concerning decline in job satisfaction among library personnel, which is influenced by multiple factors including a lack of job security, insufficient recognition, limited career advancement opportunities, inadequate work environments, slow promotion processes, and non-competitive salary packages (Okhakhu and Omoike, 2017; Yaya, 2016). Research across various organisational settings has consistently shown that employee dissatisfaction is linked to decreased motivation and increased turnover rates in the workforce (e.g., Ikonne and Yacob, 2014; Opeke et al., 2019). These challenges significantly affect job satisfaction levels among librarians and can undermine the overall effectiveness of library services. Furthermore, it is suggested that library personnel experience lower levels of motivation compared to their counterparts in other roles within the organisation, which may contribute to their declining job satisfaction. Addressing these motivational issues is vital for improving the job satisfaction of library personnel. Therefore, this research aims to investigate the correlation between staff motivation and job satisfaction among library personnel working in public university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria, building upon existing literature to provide a more comprehensive understanding of this important issue.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to investigate how staff motivation could influence the job satisfaction of library personnel in public universities in Oyo State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

1. Determine the level of job satisfaction of library personnel in public universities in Oyo State, Nigeria;
2. Find out the level of staff motivation of library personnel in public universities in Oyo State, Nigeria; and
3. Ascertain the relationship that exists between staff motivation and job satisfaction of library personnel in public universities in Oyo State, Nigeria;

Research Questions

The following research questions will guide the study:

1. What is the level of job satisfaction of library personnel in public universities in Oyo State, Nigeria?
2. What is the level of staff motivation of library personnel in public universities in Oyo State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 level of significance:

Ho 1: There is no significant relationship between staff motivation and job satisfaction of library personnel in public universities in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Scope of the Study

The research focuses on public university libraries, specifically the federal and state-owned located in Oyo State of Nigeria. The study participants were limited to library personnel working in these public university libraries across the Oyo State of Nigeria. Support staff members in the libraries were not included in the study. The researchers believed that library personnel are custodians of the information resources within the university libraries, and they play a significant role in relating with the administration and the library patrons. The researchers evaluated library personnel's levels of job satisfaction by examining specific indicators of staff motivation, such as autonomy, competence, and relatedness.

Literature Review

Job satisfaction plays a pivotal role in the success of any organisation. In a study by Oyovwevotu (2017), it was discovered that job satisfaction levels among librarians in public universities in Nigeria were notably low. Conversely, Opeke et al. (2019) reported high levels of job satisfaction among library personnel. Baro et al. (2013) conducted a study on the job satisfaction levels of cataloguer librarians in university libraries in Nigeria. The findings indicated that cataloguers in Nigerian university libraries expressed dissatisfaction with their roles, responsibilities, workplace culture, rewards, performance evaluations, and development opportunities. Similarly, Saka and Salman (2014) examined the motivation and job satisfaction of library personnel, revealing that staff morale was dampened by frustrations stemming from limited involvement in decision-making processes and other factors. Badia and Madawaki (2016) found that job satisfaction

levels among library staff were low, with a majority of respondents expressing dissatisfaction with their roles.

On the other hand, Yaya et al. (2016) investigated, job satisfaction among librarians in academic libraries in Nigeria and found that respondents generally reported a commendable level of job satisfaction. Thornton (2000) identified sources of dissatisfaction and satisfaction among librarians, shedding light on areas that impact their job contentment. Adio and Popoola (2010) highlighted the significant influence of job satisfaction on the career commitment of librarians in federal university libraries. Amune (2013) explored job motivation as a predictor of job satisfaction among library personnel, revealing that motivational factors significantly influenced staff satisfaction, irrespective of their professional status. The study indicated that salary, library policies, administrative support, career advancement opportunities, personal growth, and job security were key sources of satisfaction for library staff.

In a study by Ikonne and Yacob (2014) on the influence of spatial comfort and environmental workplace ergonomics on the job satisfaction of librarians in Federal and State university libraries in Southern Nigeria, a positive relationship between ergonomics and job satisfaction was observed. The research design adopted for the study was survey-based, providing valuable insights into the factors influencing job satisfaction among librarians in the Nigerian university library system.

Motivation stems from individuals' needs, desires, wants, or drives, making it a multifaceted concept influenced by various factors such as personal job expectations and self-esteem at the individual level, and organisational aspects like job security, salary, and benefits. It comprises biological, emotional, social, and cognitive elements that propel behaviour. According to Okhakhu and Omoike (2017), motivation encompasses both internal and external forces that fuel individuals' desire and energy to remain consistently engaged and committed to their work, roles, or goals. There are two main types of motivation: extrinsic and intrinsic. Extrinsic motivation involves completing tasks or responding to external stimuli like avoiding punishment or receiving rewards. On the other hand, intrinsic motivation stems from internal feelings such as satisfaction and pride in one's work. It is the drive to work diligently solely for the joy of accomplishing a task, driven by personal competence and self-determination rather than external rewards (Adetayo and Babarinde, 2023).

Studies by Panagiotopoulos et al. (2018) as well as Adeoye and Fields (2014) have shown that motivation significantly impacts employees' job satisfaction, particularly in the realm of compensation management. Neglecting motivation within a library setting can impede the achievement of the management's objectives (Adetayo and Babarinde, 2023), as the quality of a university library is inherently linked to the passion and performance of its staff. In Nigeria, library management often falls short in prioritising employee training, professional development, and financial rewards, leading to dissatisfaction among librarians, as highlighted by Adetayo and Hamzat (2021). This financial strain is exacerbated by the lack of government and organisational support, particularly in underdeveloped countries like Nigeria, impacting library personnel. Unfortunately, there is a dearth of platforms for employees to voice their concerns and challenges.

Given these challenges, it is crucial to focus on addressing the problems faced by library personnel in public university libraries in Oyo state, Nigeria, as the state's characteristics are pertinent to the study's objectives. By addressing these issues, universities can enhance employee motivation, job satisfaction, and overall performance in their library.

Theoretical Frameworks

For this study on correlational analysis of staff motivation and job satisfaction among library personnel in public universities in Oyo State, Nigeria, the theories that were employed to underpin the discussion of variables were Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory and Self-Determination Theory (SDT).

1. Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory: Herzberg's theory distinguishes between motivators that lead to satisfaction and hygiene factors that prevent dissatisfaction in the workplace. By applying this theory, the study was able to explore how factors like recognition, achievement, and growth opportunities impact job satisfaction, while aspects such as working conditions and salary influence dissatisfaction levels among library personnel in Oyo State's public universities.
2. Self-determination theory posits that individuals have three basic psychological needs: autonomy, competence, and relatedness. When these needs are satisfied, individuals are more likely to be intrinsically motivated, leading to higher levels of engagement, job satisfaction, and performance. In the context of library personnel, applying the

Self-Determination Theory can help researchers understand how factors such as autonomy in task assignments, opportunities for skill development (competence), and positive relationships with colleagues and supervisors (relatedness) influence staff motivation. By aligning the study with the Self-Determination Theory, the researchers were able to explore how satisfying these basic psychological needs can enhance intrinsic motivation and job satisfaction among library personnel in public universities in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Conceptual Model

The conceptual model adopted for this study is built on the theories and literature that were reviewed. The model is broadly divided into two parts: Staff motivation and job satisfaction of library personnel in the university library. Staff motivation has been described as the internal and external factors that drive employees to engage in behaviours that contribute to the achievement of organisational goals (Panagiotopoulos et al., 2018) staff motivation factors consist of indicators such as autonomy, competence, and relatedness.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model for the Study.
Source: The Researchers, 2024.

A library personnel's level of motivation is inched on these three indicators; they could be a strong determinant of their efforts, doggedness, and job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is crucial to every worker in any organisation; this is because it increases the efficiency of workers in the organisation. Indicators of job satisfaction include recognition, leadership styles, career advancement opportunities, a conducive work environment employee promotion, and remuneration. Consequently, if library personnel are adequately motivated in the library, there is the tendency that such library personnel would be happy being in the profession, and therefore his/her degree of satisfaction on the job is likely to increase tremendously. Several

studies conducted in the area of job satisfaction attested to the fact that a motivated worker is a satisfied one (Ahmed, 2014; van Scheers and Botha, 2014).

Methodology

Research Design

The survey research design was adopted for the study. A survey as a research design determines the relationship between two or more variables and the strength of this relationship (Cheng, 2016). Hence, the survey research design was adopted for the study to find out the relationships between staff motivation and job satisfaction.

Population

The population for this study comprised all the 139 library personnel in the 4 public universities (federal and state) in Oyo State, Nigeria. The researchers surveyed all the library personnel (librarians and library officers) in all the public university libraries established in the Oyo State of Nigeria. The universities are as listed: University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomoso, Technical University, Ibadan, and Emmanuel Alayande University of Education, Oyo. The detail is as shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Figures of University Libraries and Library Personnel in Oyo State, Nigeria.

S/N	Universities	Librarians	Library Officer	Library Personnel	Administered Questionnaire	Retrieved Questionnaire	%	Cumulative %
1	University of Ibadan, Ibadan	26	42	68	64	52	46.4	46.4
2	Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomoso	20	20	40	40	38	33.9	80.3
3	Technical University, Ibadan	3	0	3	1	1	0.9	81.2
4	Emmanuel Alayande University of Education, Oyo	7	21	28	25	21	18.8	100
Total				139	130	112	100	

Source: Field Survey 2024.

Table 1 presents the 139 library personnel (librarians and library officers) from the four public universities (University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomoso, Technical University, Ibadan, and Emmanuel Alayande University of Education, Oyo) that participated in the study.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The total enumeration technique was used for this study. The researchers were interested in utilizing the total population in the state because of its manageable size. This means that the researchers surveyed all the library personnel in all the public university libraries established in the Oyo State of Nigeria. This is to give a wider coverage of all the library personnel working in all public (federal and state) universities in the state slated for the study.

Research Instrument

The researchers employed a questionnaire to collect the data for this study. A part of the questionnaire (job satisfaction) was adapted from Arinola (2020), the aspect of staff motivation was

designed by the researchers and the questionnaire was tagged “Staff Motivation and Job Satisfaction of library Personnel in Public Universities in Oyo State, Nigeria”. The researchers postulated two research questions for the study and designed the questionnaire along with the identified research questions. The research instrument is divided into four sections: A, B, C, and D. Items in the instrument have been gathered from the literature reviewed for the study. Section A: Demographic information of the library personnel such as age, gender, marital status, educational qualification, designation, and length of service were inquired in this aspect. Section B: Level of job satisfaction. This section contained six items: employee recognition, good leadership styles, career advancement opportunities, a conducive work environment, employee promotion opportunities, and remuneration. Respondents were required to choose from available options regarding their job satisfaction. They were to assess library personnel on a 4-point Likert-type assessment scale, viz: Very high level = 4; High level = 3; Low level = 2 and zero level = 1. Section C: This section elicited information on the level of staff motivation of library personnel. It

was evaluated based on the following subheadings: Autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Items were developed by the researchers on factors affecting the Level of staff motivation (SM) of library personnel. Respondents were to assess library personnel on a 4-point Likert-type assessment scale, viz: Very high level = 4; High level = 3; Low level = 2 and zero level =1.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The validity of the instrument was tested to ensure that it accurately measured the construct developed for the study. To ensure the validity of the instrument for this study, therefore, the researchers with the assistance of some experienced experts in

the areas of the variables under study scrutinized the questionnaire. Based on the experts' useful feedback, the research instrument was modified where necessary. A pilot study was conducted. The researchers carried out the pilot study at the University of Ilorin, and 45 copies of the questionnaire were distributed among the library personnel. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach's Alpha of 0.7 and above. Cronbach's alpha of below 0.7 indicates a low level of internal consistency among the items in the research instrument. However, Cronbach's alpha of 0.7 and above implies a high level of internal consistency among the items in the research instrument (Khanal and Poudel, 2017). The result of the reliability test is shown in Table 2 below:

Table 2: Pilot Test of Reliability of the Research Instrument.

S/N	Survey Item	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
1	Job satisfaction	0.84	29
2	Staff motivation	0.95	16

Research Procedure and Method of Data Collection

The corrected copies of the questionnaire were administered to library personnel in all the public university libraries slated for the study. The respondents were assured that information supplied by them would be treated with the utmost confidentiality and used solely for academic research. The researchers with the help of 3 research assistants that were personally trained by the researchers administered the copies of the questionnaire to the library personnel in the various university libraries. The researchers also adopted the use of electronic administration of the instrument to some respondents. Friends working in most of the university libraries equally assisted, and even the university librarians were also engaged to add credibility to the data collected and analysed for the study. On the whole, 130 copies of the questionnaire were administered to library personnel in all 4 public university libraries slated for the study; out of which, a total number of 112 copies were retrieved. This gives an 86.2% return rate of the administered research instrument for the study.

Method of Data Analysis

The data from the research questionnaire

was analysed using version 22 of the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS). The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequency distribution, percentages, mean, and standard deviation, especially for research questions. The hypothesis was tested using Pearson Product Moment correlation (PPMC) analysis. The result was used to attest to the mutual relationships that existed between staff motivation and job satisfaction variables in the study.

Findings of the Study

The findings show the demographic information of the respondents as well as their responses to a series of questions based on the Likert scale and the results of the correlational analysis. Table 3 presents the demographic characteristics of the respondents. The data reveals that 61 (54.5%) respondents were male, while 51 (45.5%) were female, indicating a higher representation of male participants in the study. The age distribution among the respondents varied: 6 participants (5.4%) were in the 20-25 age bracket, 12 (10.7%) were aged 26-30, 36 (32.1%) fell within the 31-35 age bracket, and 58 (51.8%) were 36 years and above, suggesting a predominant presence of older library personnel, particularly those aged 36 and above. Furthermore, the data indicated that a significant proportion

of respondents were married, with 76 (67.9%) respondents indicated being married, while 29 (25.9%) were single. This marital status breakdown implies a status of maturity and responsibility on the part of the library personnel in fulfilling their roles towards library users in the different university libraries. In terms of educational qualifications, 32 (28.6%) respondents held a Master's Degree in Library and Information Science (MLIS), while 43 (38.3%) had a Bachelor's Degree in Library and Information Science. This suggests that over 70%

of the respondents were professionally qualified librarians. Additionally, slightly over 12% of the respondents had obtained PhD degrees, indicating that more than 80% of library personnel in public university libraries in Oyo State did not hold a PhD. This observation raises concerns. Especially considering the crucial role of information in today's knowledge-driven society and its potential impact on the recognition of library personnel in academic environments.

Table 3: Demographic Distribution of Respondents.

Variables		Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Gender	Male	61	54.5	54.5
	Female	51	45.5	100
	Total	112	100	
Age	20-25	6	5.4	5.4
	26-30	12	10.7	16.1
	31-35	36	32.1	48.2
	36 and above	58	51.8	100
	Total	112	100	
Marital Status	Single	29	25.9	25.9
	Married	76	67.9	93.8
	Divorced	4	3.6	97.4
	Widow	2	1.8	99.2
	Widower	1	0.9	100
	Total	112	100	
Highest Educational Qualification	Ph.D.	14	12.5	12.5
	MLIS	32	28.6	41.1
	BLIS	43	38.3	79.4
	Diploma	23	20.5	100
	Total	112	100	
Designation	UL	2	1.8	1.8
	Deputy UL	3	2.7	4.5
	Principal Librarian	12	10.7	15.2
	Librarian I	24	21.4	36.6
	Librarian II	18	16.1	52.7
	Asst. Librarian	26	23.2	75.9
	Library Officer	27	24.1	100
	Total	112	100	
Length of Service	Below 6 years	11	9.8	9.8
	6-10	35	31.3	41.1
	11-15	25	22.3	63.4
	16 and above	41	36.6	100
	Total	112	100	

Source: Field Survey 2024.

The only hypothesis of the study was analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) analysis, which aimed to evaluate the correlation or differences between the independent variable and the dependent variable. The outcome derived from this analysis was utilised to confirm the interrelationship between the variables (staff

motivation and job satisfaction) in the study.

Analysis of the Research Questions

Research Question One: What is the level of job satisfaction of library personnel in public universities in Oyo State, Nigeria?

Table 4: Level of Job Satisfaction of Respondents.

S/N	Statement	VHL(%)	HL(%)	LL(%)	ZL(%)	X	S D	AM
Autonomy								
I	I have the freedom to make decisions related to my work in the library.	44 (39.3%)	38 (33.9%)	20 (17.9%)	10 (8.9%)	3.04	0.72	3.07 1st
Ii	I can choose how to accomplish my tasks and responsibilities in the library.	42 (37.5%)	55 (49.1%)	10 (8.9%)	5 (4.5%)	3.20	0.73	
Iiii	Autonomy in my work significantly impacts my motivation as a library personnel	35 (31.3%)	45 (40.2%)	20 (17.9%)	12 (10.7%)	2.92	0.83	
Iv	Autonomy plays a crucial role in determining my level of job satisfaction as a library staff member.	47 (41.9%)	35 (31.3%)	25 (22.3%)	5 (4.5%)	3.11	0.85	
Competence								
I	I am confident in my ability to perform my job duties effectively in the library.	41 (36.6%)	43 (38.4%)	10 (8.9%)	18 (16.1%)	2.96	0.90	2.96 2nd
Ii	My skills and knowledge are utilized to their fullest potential in my role as a library personnel.	49 (43.8%)	33 (29.5%)	22 (37.5%)	8 (7.1%)	3.10	0.85	
Iiii	Receiving feedback on my performance significantly contributes to my motivation in the library.	50 (44.5%)	26 (22.2%)	15 (13.4%)	21 (18.8%)	2.94	0.81	
Iv	A sense of competence in my work positively impacts my overall job satisfaction as a library staff member.	20 (17.9%)	63 (56.3%)	20 (17.9%)	9 (8.0%)	2.84	0.82	
Relatedness								
I	I feel connected to my colleagues and supervisors in the library.	26 (23.2%)	37 (33.0%)	30 (26.8%)	19 (16.9%)	2.62	0.97	2.65 3rd
Ii	Strong relationships with my co-workers positively affect my motivation at work.	46 (41.1%)	29 (25.9%)	32 (28.6%)	5 (4.5%)	3.04	0.84	
Iiii	A sense of belonging and camaraderie in the workplace influences my job satisfaction.	23 (20.5%)	36 (32.1%)	40 (35.7%)	13 (11.6%)	2.62	0.97	
Iv	Building positive relationships with others in the library is important for my overall staff motivation.	7 (6.3%)	31 (27.7%)	61 (54.5%)	13 (11.6%)	2.30	0.98	
Overall mean score = 2.89								
Field Survey, 2024								
Key: VHL = Very High level, HL = High Level, LL = Low Level, OL = Zero level, M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation; AM = Average Mean								
**Decision Rule: if mean falls between 1–1.49 = Zero level; 1.5–2.49 = Low Level; 2.5–3.49 = High level; 3.5–4 = Very High level								

Table 5: Level of Staff Motivation of Respondents.

S/N	Statement	VHL(%)	HL(%)	LL(%)	ZL(%)	X	S D	AM
Autonomy								
I	I have the freedom to make decisions related to my work in the library.	44 (39.3%)	38 (33.9%)	20 (17.9%)	10 (8.9%)	3.04	0.72	3.07 1st
Ii	I can choose how to accomplish my tasks and responsibilities in the library.	42 (37.5%)	55 (49.1%)	10 (8.9%)	5 (4.5%)	3.20	0.73	
Iiii	Autonomy in my work significantly impacts my motivation as a library personnel	35 (31.3%)	45 (40.2%)	20 (17.9%)	12 (10.7%)	2.92	0.83	
Iv	Autonomy plays a crucial role in determining my level of job satisfaction as a library staff member.	47 (41.9%)	35 (31.3%)	25 (22.3%)	5 (4.5%)	3.11	0.85	
Competence								
I	I am confident in my ability to perform my job duties effectively in the library.	41 (36.6%)	43 (38.4%)	10 (8.9%)	18 (16.1%)	2.96	0.90	2.96 2nd
Ii	My skills and knowledge are utilized to their fullest potential in my role as a library personnel.	49 (43.8%)	33 (29.5%)	22 (37.5%)	8 (7.1%)	3.10	0.85	
Iiii	Receiving feedback on my performance significantly contributes to my motivation in the library.	50 (44.5%)	26 (22.2%)	15 (13.4%)	21 (18.8%)	2.94	0.81	
Iv	A sense of competence in my work positively impacts my overall job satisfaction as a library staff member.	20 (17.9%)	63 (56.3%)	20 (17.9%)	9 (8.0%)	2.84	0.82	
Relatedness								
I	I feel connected to my colleagues and supervisors in the library.	26 (23.2%)	37 (33.0%)	30 (26.8%)	19 (16.9%)	2.62	0.97	2.65 3rd
Ii	Strong relationships with my co-workers positively affect my motivation at work.	46 (41.1%)	29 (25.9%)	32 (28.6%)	5 (4.5%)	3.04	0.84	
Iiii	A sense of belonging and camaraderie in the workplace influences my job satisfaction.	23 (20.5%)	36 (32.1%)	40 (35.7%)	13 (11.6%)	2.62	0.97	
Iv	Building positive relationships with others in the library is important for my overall staff motivation.	7 (6.3%)	31 (27.7%)	61 (54.5%)	13 (11.6%)	2.30	0.98	
Overall mean score = 2.89								
Field Survey, 2024								
Key: VHL = Very High level, HL = High Level, LL = Low Level, OL = Zero level, M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation; AM = Average Mean								
**Decision Rule: if mean falls between 1–1.49 = Zero level; 1.5–2.49 = Low Level; 2.5–3.49 = High level; 3.5–4 = Very High level								

Table 5 addressed staff motivation among library personnel in public university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria. The data illustrates that employees in these libraries are satisfied with the level of autonomy they have, as reflected in an average mean score of 3.07. Specifically, statements such as “I can choose how to accomplish my tasks and responsibilities in the library” (mean of 3.20) and “Autonomy plays a crucial role in determining my level of job satisfaction as a library staff member” (mean of 3.11) highlight this satisfaction. Moreover, respondents indicated their freedom to make decisions related to their work in the library, scoring an average mean of 3.04. Additionally, some respondents (with an average mean of 2.96) felt that their skills and knowledge are effectively utilized in their role as library personnel (mean of 3.10). Similarly, feedback on their performance was noted to be a significant motivator for some respondents, as indicated by a mean score of 2.94. For more detailed information, please refer to the table. The following steps were followed to calculate the Mean and Standard Deviation (SD) for Tables 4 and 5:

1. Mean Calculation:

The mean for each statement is calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Mean } (X) = \frac{\sum(f \times x)}{N}$$

Where:

- f = frequency of each response category
- x = value assigned to each response category (e.g., 1 for Very Low Level, 2 for Low Level, 3 for High Level and 4, for Very High Level)
- N = total number of responses

For instance, if a statement received the following responses:

- Very High level (code = 4): 34 responses
- High level (code = 3): 48 responses
- low level (code = 2): 28 responses
- Very low level (code = 1): 2 responses

The calculation would be:

$$\frac{X=(34 \times 4)+(48 \times 3)+(28 \times 2)+(2 \times 1)}{34+48+28+2}$$

$$X=3.02$$

2. Standard Deviation Calculation:

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(f \times (x - \text{Mean})^2)}{N}}$$

Where:

- f = frequency of each response category
- x = value assigned to each response category
- Mean = mean calculated previously
- N = total number of responses

Following the previous example, once the mean is calculated, substitute the mean into the standard deviation formula to compute SD accordingly:

1. For each response category, calculate $(x - \text{Mean})^2$.
2. Multiply each $(x - \text{Mean})^2$ by the corresponding frequency f .
3. Sum these values and divide by N .
4. Take the square root of that value to get the SD.

Overall Mean Amount

After calculating the mean for each statement, the overall mean score (2.81) was derived by averaging the individual statement means.

Decision Rule

The predetermined level of significance for the study is 0.05. It is assumed that there is no significant correlation between the variables being studied if the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 ($p < 0.05$), leading to the rejection of the hypothesis.

Hypothesis 1

The only hypothesis aimed to investigate the correlation between staff motivation and job satisfaction among library personnel in public university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria. The findings are presented in Table 6, using the Pearson Product Moment correlation (PPMC) analysis.

Table 6: Showing Correlation between Staff Motivation and Job Satisfaction of Library Personnel in Public Universities in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-value**	P	Remark
Job Satisfaction	112	2.89	0.79	0.420	.000c	Sig.
Staff Motivation	112	2.81	0.84			
Significant at 0.05 level.						
Key: N: Population, r: Value, P: Level of significance						
Source: Field survey, 2024						

Based on the data presented in Table 6, the mean of job satisfaction among library personnel in public Universities in Oyo state, Nigeria was 2.89 with a standard deviation of 0.79. Similarly, the mean staff motivation of library personnel was 2.81, with a standard deviation of 0.84. The correlation coefficient

obtained was 0.420, with p-values of .000, indicating a significant positive correlation between Staff Motivation and Job Satisfaction among library personnel in public Universities in Oyo state, Nigeria, where $P < 0.05$. The analysis of the data ($r = 0.420$, $N=112$, $P < 0.05$) Hence the null hypothesis for the study is rejected. This signifies that a significant relationship exists between staff motivation and job satisfaction among library personnel in public Universities in Oyo state, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The discussion follows the research questions, establishing the connections between staff motivation and job satisfaction among library personnel based on past empirical studies. The study focused on two research questions and a single hypothesis to understand the impact of staff motivation on the job satisfaction of library personnel in public universities in Oyo State, Nigeria. The study's findings are outlined as follows: Research question one aimed to assess the level of job satisfaction among library personnel in public university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria. The results revealed that library personnel considered opportunities for regular promotion and effective management styles as key factors contributing to their job satisfaction within the university system. These findings were supported by Tella and Ibinaiye (2019), who also noted high job satisfaction levels among librarians. Similarly, a study on leadership styles, staff motivation, and job satisfaction by Adetayo and Babarinde (2023) found that library personnel in private universities in Osun State were satisfied with the promotion opportunities available. However, it is important to note that a previous study in Osun State highlighted dissatisfaction among librarians regarding finance (Adetayo and Hamzat, 2021).

Research question two revealed that library personnel were motivated by the autonomy they enjoyed in their work, significantly contributing to their motivation levels. This aligns with the findings of Bamgbose and Ladipo (2017), who identified various motivational factors such as job security, wages, relationships with colleagues, staff appraisal, financial incentives, and rewards available to library employees, all of which influenced their performance. Similarly, the study by Lamptey et al. (2013) reported high motivational levels among library personnel, attributing it to factors like recognition of hard work, equal conditions of service, opportunities for career advancement, and involvement in decision-making processes.

Moreover, as revealed from the findings of the only hypothesis tested, the null hypothesis was rejected. This indicated that a significant relationship exists between staff motivation and job satisfaction among library personnel in public university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria. This finding is consistent with previous studies by researchers such as Tella et al. (2007), Fanimihin and Popoola (2013) and Adetayo and Babarinde (2023), who emphasised the impact of work motivation, rewards, and recognition on job satisfaction independent of job characteristics. These studies also highlighted the high motivation levels among library personnel in Nigeria, despite challenges such as heavy workloads and poor incentives.

Summary of Findings

The main objective of this study was to investigate how staff motivation correlates with the job satisfaction of library personnel in public universities in Oyo State, Nigeria. The major findings of the study are as follows:

1. Library personnel in public university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria, saw their level of job satisfaction as high. They ascribed this to regular promotion opportunities received as well as good management styles in operation in their library as the greatest measure of their job satisfaction in the university system.
2. Library personnel's level of staff motivation was similarly high. They ascribed this to the level of autonomy they have, and the ability to choose how to accomplish their tasks and responsibilities in the library. These supported their level of staff motivation in the university library.
3. Similarly, staff motivation has a positive significant influence on the job satisfaction of library personnel in public universities in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Conclusion

Job satisfaction holds significant importance within public university libraries, necessitating a high level of commitment from university administration to ensure optimal satisfaction among library personnel. While previous research has highlighted the link between staff motivation and job satisfaction, this current study successfully challenges earlier assumptions regarding low job satisfaction levels among library personnel. The findings of this study reveal a positive correlation between staff motivation and job

satisfaction among library personnel in public university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria. Furthermore, the study reinforces the notion that job satisfaction plays a pivotal role in enhancing the efficiency of workers, particularly within public university libraries in Oyo State, where a satisfied employee is a productive one. It underscores the need for prioritizing the welfare and personal concerns of library personnel in these public-funded institutions, emphasising the importance of genuine motivation to facilitate optimal performance. University authorities should actively identify and implement motivational factors that enhance job satisfaction among library personnel, recognising the impact this has on overall organisational efficiency. Therefore, the insights and recommendations derived from this study hold significant relevance for addressing the specific needs within the Oyo state in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings from this study, the following recommendations are put forward as a pathway for progress:

1. Recognising the potential lack of motivation among library personnel, attributed to the poor relationships with others in the library, which is considered important for overall staff motivation. The university administration should establish a conducive atmosphere that fosters and supports positive relationships among library personnel.
2. The study also revealed that the job satisfaction of library personnel in Oyo state, Nigerian public university libraries is hindered by disparities in the payment of allowances compared to other staff members. Consequently, it is recommended that university authorities ensure equitable treatment for all staff members, eliminating any form of discrimination or preferential treatment.
3. Lastly, library personnel should be accorded due recognition as vital custodians and providers of information resources crucial for supporting the educational curricula across all academic programs within the university system.

References

- Adeoye, A. O. and Fields, Z. (2014). Compensation Management and Employee Job Satisfaction: A Case of Nigeria. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 41(3): 345-352. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09718923.2014.11893369>
- Adetayo, A. J. and Babarinde, O. A. (2023). Leadership styles, staff motivation and job satisfaction in private university libraries in Osun State, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, article no. 7576. [Online]. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/7576>
- Adetayo, A. J. and Hamzat, S. A. (2021). Infopreneurship and Financial Satisfaction Among Library Professionals in Tertiary Institutions in Ede, Osun, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, article no. 4749. [Online]. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/4749>
- Adewoyin, O. O., Ehioghae, M. and Olorunsaye, J. O. (2020). Occupational Stress Among Library Personnel in Public Universities in Nigeria. *Library and Information Perspectives and Research*, 2(1): 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.47524/lipr.v2i1.1>
- Adio, G. and Popoola, S. O. (2010). Job satisfaction and career commitment of librarians in federal university libraries in Nigeria. *Library Review*, 59(3): 175-184. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00242531011031160>
- Ahmed, Y. A. (2014). *Job satisfaction and job performance with moderating effect of Islamic work ethics in Yemen* [Doctoral dissertation, Universiti Utara Malaysia]. <https://etd.uum.edu.my/5292/1/s91764.pdf>
- Amune, J. B. (2013). Job Motivation As A Predictor Of Job Satisfaction Among Professional And Non- Professional Library Staff In Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma. *International Journal of Innovative Research & Development*, 2(5): 1477-1497. https://www.internationaljournalcorner.com/index.php/ijird_ojs/article/view/133498
- Badia, M. Z.-B. and Madawaki, Z. (2016). Salary/fringe benefit as correlation of job commitment of librarians in federal university libraries in the north-eastern Nigeria. *Nigerian Libraries*, 49(1-2): 92-100. <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/jnla/article/view/163492>
- Bamgbose, A. A. and Ladipo, S. O. (2017). Influence of motivation on academic library employees' performance and productivity in Lagos, Nigeria. *Information Impact: Journal of Information and Knowledge Management*, 8(2): 33-47. <https://doi.org/10.4314/ijikm.v8i2.3>
- Baro, E. E., Fyneman, B. and Zoukemefa, T. (2013). Job Satisfaction among Cataloger Librarians in University Libraries in Nigeria. *Cataloging &*

- Classification Quarterly*, 51(6): 675-696. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01639374.2013.773952>
- Cheng, T. (2016, April 28). *Research Methods Part 4: The Correlational Design*. Retrieved February 10, 2024 from <https://www.psych2go.net/research-methods-part-4-the-correlational-%09design>
- Dina, T. and Olowosoke, G. O. (2018). The Effect of Motivation and Job Performance on Library Personnel Effectiveness in Universities Libraries in Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, article no. 2042. [Online]. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/2042>
- Edeh, I. N. (2010). *Influence of School Climate on Teachers' Motivation in Secondary Schools in Enugu-East Education Zone of Enugu State* [Doctoral dissertation, UNN]. <https://repository.unn.edu.ng:8080/xmlui/handle/123456789/5588>
- Ezeamama, I. G. (2019). Job Satisfaction and Employee Productivity in Anambra State Nigeria. *European Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 7(2): 1-13. <https://www.idpublications.org/ejrss-vol-7-no-2-2019>
- Fanimihin, A. O. and Popoola, S. O. (2013). Effects of career progression, work motivation and leadership styles on job satisfaction of library personnel in the Federal Civil Service of Nigeria. *International Journal of Library and Information Science*, 5(5): 147-159. <https://doi.org/10.5897/IJLIS.9000033>
- Ikonne, C. N. and Yacob, H. (2014). Influence of Spatial Comfort and Environmental Workplace Ergonomics on Job Satisfaction of Librarians in the Federal and State University Libraries in Southern Nigeria. *Open Access Library Journal*, 1: e814. <https://doi.org/10.4236/oalib.1100814>
- Khanal, L. and Poudel, S. R. (2017). Knowledge Management, Employee Satisfaction and Performance: Empirical Evidence From Nepal. *Saudi Journal of Business and Management Studies*, 2(2): 82-91. <https://doi.org/10.21276/sjbms.2017.2.2.3>
- Lampsey, R. B., Boateng, M. S. and Antwi, I. K. (2013). Motivation and Performance of Librarians in Public Universities in Ghana. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, article no. 911. [Online]. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/911>
- Mabaso, C. M. and Dlamini, B. I. (2017). Impact of Compensation and Benefits on Job Satisfaction. *Research Journal of Business Management*, 11(2): 80-90. <https://doi.org/10.3923/rjbm.2017.80.90>
- Okhakhu, O. D. and Omoike, A. D. (2017). Job Motivation, Satisfaction and Its Effects on Library Officers' Productivity in Three Selected Libraries in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Information Science and Technology*, 10(1): 52-61. https://www.jaistonline.org/vol10no1_2017.html
- Opeke, R., Ikonne, C. N. and Adewoyin, O. O. (2019). Job Satisfaction among Library Personnel in Public Universities in South-West Nigeria. *Information Impact: Journal of Information and Knowledge Management*, 10(2): 124-138. <https://doi.org/10.4314/ijikm.v10i2.9>
- Oyovwevotu, L. (2017). *Institutional Support, Job Satisfaction and Employees' Commitment In Public University Libraries in South-East Geo-Political Zone, Nigeria* [Doctoral dissertation, Babcock University].
- Panagiotopoulos, G., Petta, E. and Karanikola, Z. (2018). The Contribution of Motivation to Job Satisfaction: A Survey of Technological Educational Institute Employees of Western Greece. *European Journal of Training and Development Studies*, 5(3): 18-26. <https://doi.org/10.37745/ejtds.2014>
- Saka, K. A. and Salman, A. A. (2014). An Assessment of the Levels of Job Motivation and Satisfaction as Predictors of Job Performance of Library Personnel in Nigerian Universities. *Journal of Balkan Libraries Union*, 2(2): 26-33. <https://doi.org/10.16918/bluj.34774>
- Tella, A., Ayeni, C. O. and Popoola, S. O. (2007). Work Motivation, Job Satisfaction, and Organisational Commitment of Library Personnel in Academic and Research Libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, article no. 118. [Online]. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/118>
- Tella, A. and Ibinaiye, O. A. (2019). Correlates of staff motivation, satisfaction, and job performance of library staff in selected Nigerian University libraries. *The International Information & Library Review*, 52(1): 32-49. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10572317.2019.1631691>
- Thornton, J. K. (2000). Job Satisfaction of Librarians of African Descent Employed in ARL Academic Libraries. *College & Research Libraries*, 61(3):

217-232. <https://doi.org/10.5860/crl.61.3.217>

- van Scheers, L. and Botha, J. (2014). Analysing Relationship Between Employee Job Satisfaction and Motivation. *Journal of Business and Retail Management Research*, 9(1): 98-109. <https://doi.org/10.24052/JBRMR/186>
- Yaya, J. A. (2016). The Effect of Human Capital Development on Job Satisfaction of Librarians in Public Universities in Nigeria. *American Journal of Business and Society*, 1(3): 98-117. <https://files.aiscience.org/journal/article/pdf/70380048.pdf>
- Yaya, J. A., Opeke, R. O. and Onuoha, U. D. (2016). Job Satisfaction as Correlates of Librarians' productivity in Public University Libraries in Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, article no. 1418. [Online]. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1418>

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